

ISSUES OF IMPROVING PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract: In the article, the application and effective use of advanced pedagogical technologies in the duration of training for students in preschool educational organizations is focused on the methodological foundations of education and training, and the specifics of strengthening, organization and improvement of pedagogical aspects of education of students through multimedia, animation, computer technologies are explained.

Keywords: Education, preschool educational organizations, pedagogical technologies, innovative developments, electronic methodological tools, interactive instructions, modern methods, foreign and Uzbek scientists, recommendations, methodological foundations.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация: В статье применение и эффективное использование передовых педагогических технологий в процессе обучения обучающихся в дошкольных образовательных организациях сосредоточено на методических основах воспитания и обучения, а также на специфике укрепления, организации и совершенствования педагогических аспектов обучение студентов через мультимедии, анимацию, компьютерные технологии.

Ключевые слова: Образование, дошкольные образовательные организации, педагогические технологии, инновационные разработки, электронные методические средства, интерактивные инструкции, современные методики, зарубежные и узбекские ученые, рекомендации, методические основы.

INTRODUCTION

Article 11 of the Law "On Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan states: "Preschool education has the goal of forming a healthy and mature child's personality, prepared for general secondary education schools. This education is carried out in families, kindergartens and other educational institutions regardless of the form of ownership until the age of 6-7 years [1].

According to the Decree No. PF-6108 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of November 6, 2020 "On measures to develop the fields of education and science in the period of new development of Uzbekistan" and the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 No. PQ-4884 "On measures to improve the education system further ", the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development, together with the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education and other ministries and agencies, set the task of introducing modern forms of teaching, new pedagogical and information technologies in the preschool education system by January 1, 2022 [3] .

In the article 53 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 16, 2019 No. ORQ-595 "On Preschool Education and Training" the tasks of introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies into the educational process, developing and producing teaching-methodical and didactic materials for educational organizations, conducting scientific research in the field of preschool education and upbringing are defined.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We all know that the problem of education is characterized by its antiquity. It was also considered in the works of Western and Eastern thinkers in the Middle Ages. Uzbek thinkers such as Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Ahmad Yugnaki, Jalaluddin Davani, Alisher Navoi contributed to world science and culture with their works. Also, foreign scientists have given a number of opinions and considerations in their scientific works.

In particular, according to Russian pedagogues: V.P. Bepalko, V.S. Bezrukova, B.L. Farberman, M.W. Clarin, M.J. Aristanov, S.L. Novoselova [4], I.Yu and Hunters [6], researches on the use of computers in the educational process show not only that the possibility of using computer technologies is appropriate, but also that it has a special place in the development of the child's intellect and personality, and today the use of multimedia teaching tools reliably proves many methodological innovations in the preschool education system [6].

I hope that multimedia products will increase the interest of students at this stage of education, will create an opportunity for independent learning and intellectual potential.

RESULTS

Focusing on the fact that special attention is paid to the formation of the intellectual potential of the children in the preschool education organization, which is currently operating, together with their education, we pay special attention to the upbringing of the children as spiritually mature generation. Children of a small group will have the ability to master general ideas about natural objects. Therefore, it is necessary to familiarize children with the natural objects located nearby, which are often encountered, and show the time to observe them. A small group of children of preschool age are just beginning to observe some interrelationships in nature.

Preschool education is a holistic process aimed at the comprehensive development of children, taking into account their interests, talents, individual mental and physical characteristics, cultural needs, as well as the formation of moral norms, acquisition of life and social experience. [3]

Group forms of methodical work include pedagogical readings, practical conferences, seminars on project activities, organizational-activity games, methodical development contests, theoretical seminars, and participation in the work of temporary creative groups. At the initial stage of methodical work, reproductive forms are leading, and at the final stage, heuristic and productive forms are leading.

Another component of the model is the method. The pre-school education organization requires its pupils to conduct practical work, approaching promising methods, in choosing and forming methods of traveling to nature with the help of modern methodical tools [2].

Computer games increase this curiosity feature of students. As a result, their mental development takes shape. Multimedia computer games increase the curiosity of students based on the following:

- that the game object displayed on the screen is given the effect of animation and they are constantly moving;
- sound;
- musical performances;
- animated film;
- multiplication;

Psychological-pedagogical effects with the help of this computer during the game not only increase the curiosity of young children, but also increase their desire to learn. From the

information presented above, it became clear that the effective use of information technologies, i.e., multimedia in the education of children of pre-school age, is one of the main issues of today.

The method of preparing multimedia tools and forming children's computer literacy is the main technical tool of multimedia technology of personal computers. Additional tools - CDs, various presentations, slides, etc. are required in the educational process of pre-school education.

Educational materials in multimedia are dynamic in nature and are presented with animation. Traditional visual materials used in the educational system are static in nature. For example, during the traditional method of teaching the letter A, the teacher shows a form made of paper or cardboard (static tool). When shown in a multimedia tool, the letter A vibrates on the computer (monitor) screen and attracts children's attention (dynamic tool). Currently, the development of various multimedia educational tools and their implementation in the educational process is rapidly developing.

Since the methods of using them in the educational process have not been developed in pre-school educational institutions, educators-pedagogues accept multimedia as a multimedia technology. In addition to a special institution that produces multimedia tools, it is also possible to use software and role-based multimedia tools that each teacher can prepare by themselves. Didactic tools of multimedia technology are fully compatible with the didactic requirements of education. Expected results of the methodical modeling stage of the implementation of the model: readiness of students to assess their strengths and weaknesses, designing an individual program for improving the required qualities; implementation of concepts such as formation of a positive attitude, feeling, readiness to love nature in the formation of the worldview and consciousness about nature.

It is characterized by the effectiveness and specificity of the expected results at the third - diagnostic stage of the implementation of the model.

The widespread introduction of modern pedagogical technologies into the educational process requires the teacher to act as the main organizer or consultant in this process.

Learning in large groups of pre-school education requires independent thinking, a creative approach and willful qualities in mastering the database prepared for training.

On the basis of pedagogical technologies, it is possible to implement and prepare educational stages for the preservation of nature that develops the personality.

Since it is based on the use of tools and information methods used in large group training sessions, it is necessary to clarify new mechanisms of their effective use. In-depth implementation of a systematic approach to arming with skills related to the educational process based on modern pedagogical technologies.

The main form of education is training. In the classes, students learn compare their speech with the teacher's model speech, perform the educational material, listen to the teacher's explanation and story, look at pictures, slides together, talk, participate in didactic games, sing together, listen to music, focus on a certain object and to speak in turn. During the training, children get acquainted with new knowledge (words related to connections between events and events, grammatical forms of speech), learn to perform educational tasks and evaluate their own work through the speech instruction of the educator.

The importance of educational activities conducted on the basis of pedagogical technologies can increase their interest in creative thinking, taking into account their desire to express their attitudes to problems related to life and nature [2].

The importance of effective use of this method is related to the nature of knowledge that is understandable for preschool children. Pre-school children's accumulated knowledge mainly consists of taking natural objects and events figuratively, i.e. imagining. The more colorful and clear the imagination, the more easily the child uses his imagination in practice. For this, it is necessary to take children out into the arms of nature, to observe its phenomena, to study the interactions between them [4].

There was an educational necessity for students to use innovative information and independent assessment of knowledge about nature, to eliminate problems related to nature conservation, in order to solve the problems of innovative processes and educational stages in the field of education.

In the organization and conduct of training sessions, students are encouraged to model pedagogical technologies using modern methodological tools using new methods, to solve educational problems, to understand the causes of problems related to the improvement of methodological tools, to develop their non-standard criteria, to analyze thoughts and opinions.

DISCUSSION

On the basis of the results of scientific research conducted in 2020-2022 on the results of the use of pedagogical technologies in preschool educational organizations, technologies are one of the necessary tools for organizing training at this stage of education. In such conditions, the formation of a person is fundamentally different from the previous traditional methods, which requires the development of a qualitatively new model of the preschool education system in the globalized information space, the formation of methodical works that include completely new methods that are necessary and suitable for the current conditions. The correct use of pedagogical technologies ensures the organization of educational issues, guaranteeing the successful study of children of preschool age.

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